

Kinetics and Mechanism of Dissociation and Electroreduction (at DME) of the Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes of the Macrocyclic Ligand 1,3,6,9,11,14-Hexa-azacyclohexadecane ([16]-ane-N₆) in Aqueous Solution

M. UPADHYAY, S. GANGOPADHYAY and D. BANERJEA*

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Division, University College of Science,
9½ Acharya P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

Acid catalysed dissociation of the title complexes have been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous perchlorate media. Both the complexes dissociate quite slowly; the observed rate for the copper(II) complex corresponds to $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_{\text{H}}[\text{H}^+]$, but in the nickel(II) complex the acid dependent path is absent.

The polarographic behaviour of the two complexes has also been studied using DME. In 0.1 M KCl solution, in presence of Triton X-100 as maximum suppressor, the nickel(II) complex gives a single irreversible diffusion-controlled wave corresponding to the reduction of nickel(II) to nickel(0), but the copper(II) complex gives two well separated irreversible diffusion-controlled waves each corresponding to a one-electron reduction process. These square-planar copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of the strong field ligand are reduced at the DME very much faster than the complexes of these metal ions with ethylenediamine, glycinate, etc.

MACROCYCLIC ligands usually immobilise the bound metal ion to a large extent, hence the reactivity of even labile metal ions is considerably retarded when complexed to such ligands^{1,2}. Thus in the case of the complexes of tetradentate tetraaza macrocyclic ligands, the rates of dissociation are diminished by a factor of *ca.* 10⁷ compared to those of complexes of open chain tetradentate ligands³.

A dependence of rate of dissociation on ring size has also been observed¹. In the case of the 16-membered hexaaza-nickel(II) complex, the rate of dissociation is even slower than that of the corresponding tetraaza-nickel(II) complex².

Studies on electroreduction of several copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes at dropping mercury electrode (DME) have been carried out earlier and a useful correlation had been made between the kinetic parameters for electroreduction of these complexes and their spectral (Dq) parameters^{3,4}. In view of the rather inert nature of the title complexes to dissociation, their polarographic behaviour also appeared worthy of investigation.

Experimental

Materials and reagents: The yellow coloured nickel complex was prepared by known method⁵ and its purity was checked by elemental analysis as well as uv-visible and ir spectra (Found: Ni, 11.6; N, 16.6; C, 23.6; H, 5.5. Calcd. for $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ni, 11.54; N, 16.58; C, 23.7; H, 5.35%).

A deep blue-violet coloured copper(II) complex of the ligand was prepared by refluxing an aqueous solution of bis-diethylenetriamine-copper(II) chloride with a slight excess of molar equivalent of formaldehyde solution for 2 h. The resulting solution was filtered and its volume reduced to half and the concentrate then triturated with ether when a solid product (chloride salt) separated which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The perchlorate salt of the copper(II) complex was prepared by triturating the above chloride salt with saturated NaClO₄ solution. Composition of the copper(II) complex was established by elemental analysis (Found: Cu, 12.6; N, 16.5; C, 23.3; H, 5.28. Calcd. for $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6)](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 12.44; N, 16.45; C, 23.5; H, 5.49%).

The ir spectrum of the copper(II) complex is similar to that of the nickel(II) complex indicating similar nature of both the complexes (Fig. 1).

All other chemicals used were either of reagent grade or else purified by known procedures. Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. In the kinetic experiments, ionic strength was adjusted with NaClO₄. Polarograms were run in aqueous KCl media.

Procedure: Ir spectra were recorded in KBr disc at a concentration of *ca.* 1 in 100 (w/w) using a Perkin-Elmer 599-B infrared spectrophotometer. Observations on electronic spectra were made using a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Rate of dissociation was followed spectrophotometrically, at 440 nm for the nickel(II) complex and at 550 nm

Fig. 1. Infrared spectra (ca. 1 : 100 (w/w) in KBr disc) : (A) [16]-ane-N₆, L, (B) NiL(ClO₄)₂·H₂O, and (C) CuL(ClO₄)₂·H₂O.

for the copper(II) complex, by sample quenching technique⁶. Experimental solutions were thermostated in an oil-bath at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). All observations were made under pseudo-first order conditions and the rate constants and the corresponding activation parameters were evaluated by known procedures. Systronics 304 conductometer was used for conductance measurements to evaluate the diffusion coefficients⁴ of the complex ions, $[M([16]\text{-ane-N}_6)]^{2+}$. Polarograms were recorded with a Sargent-Welch XVI polarograph and a dropping mercury electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. Solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling pure electrolytic hydrogen and polarograms were recorded in hydrogen atmosphere. Analysis of the data was made by known procedure^{8,4,7}.

Results and Discussion

Dissociation of the complexes : Both the complexes dissociate fairly slowly in acid media

(Table 1). The rate of dissociation of the nickel(II) complex is independent of acid concentration ; but the copper(II) complex shows a first order dependence on acid concentration with a concurrent acid independent path,

$$k_{obs} = k_o + k_H[H^+] \quad (1)$$

k_o is practically insensitive to ionic strength, but k_H increases appreciably with increase in ionic strength since k_H is the product of a protonation constant, K_H , and a dissociation rate constant, k'_H of the protonated species formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium,

where, S=substrate complex and P=product. This leads to $k_H = K_H \cdot k'_H$ under the condition that concentration of SH^+ is negligible compared to that of S.

The acid independent dissociation of the nickel(II) complex may be explained on the basis of

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION OF COPPER(II) AND NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES OF MACROCYCLIC LIGAND (L), [16]-ane-N₆, IN ACID MEDIA (0.01 - 1.0 M HClO₄)

[Complex] = 0.001 M, I = 1.0 M (NaClO₄ + HClO₄)

Complex	10 ⁴ k _o , s ^{-1a}				10 ⁴ k _H ¹ , s ^{-1a}			
	50°	55°	60°	70°	50°	55°	60°	70°
NiL ²⁺	0.8	—	2.00 (1.99)	6.0	—	—	—	—
CuL ²⁺	2.2	3.75	6.50 (6.95)	—	2.0	2.72	4.1 (3.1)	—

Values in parentheses are at I = 0.5 M (NaClO₄ + HClO₄).

^a k_o and k_H values have a precision of ca. $\pm 5\%$.

Complex	ΔH^\ddagger , kJ mol ⁻¹		ΔS^\ddagger , JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	
	k _o path	k _H path	k _o path	k _H path
NiL ²⁺	100.98 \pm 4.20	—	-17.76 \pm 0.78	—
CuL ²⁺	94.50 \pm 5.46	57.96 \pm 2.52	-25.93 \pm 2.18	-70.0 \pm 2.50

structural consideration. Models indicate that while these complexes are square-planar with the ligand exhibiting quadridentate function (structure A), only a slight distortion would cause the ligand to bind in a tridentate manner giving rise to a metal complex of trigonal bipyramidal structure with two

other axial ligands which can be donor solvent molecules, such as water in aqueous solution (structure B). Consideration of CFSE indicates that for a strong field ligand although nickel(II) (d^8 system) has little tendency to change from square-planar to any other geometry, the conditions are much more favourable for copper(II) (d^9 system) to assume the trigonal bipyramidal geometry⁸. In such a structure with the ligand exhibiting tridentate function the NH group which is freed from metal

binding can accept a proton in a fast pre-equilibrium to account for the acid dependent path. Since the nickel(II) complex does not show acid dependence even at a fairly high acid concentration (1.0 M HClO₄), it appears that the two unbound NH groups in the square-planar complex of this macrocyclic ligand do not have enough residual basicity for protonation to occur presumably due to their involvement in hydrogen bonding interaction with neighbouring metal bound NH groups (structure A; broken lines in A and B indicate hydrogen bonding).

Polarographic reduction of the complexes: In 0.1 M KCl medium, the nickel(II) complex gives a well defined single wave in presence of 0.002% Triton-X as maximum suppressor. The wave ($E_{1/2} = -1.35$ V vs S.C.E.) is diffusion-controlled but irreversible and corresponds to a two electron reduction of nickel(II) to nickel(0).

The copper(II) complex gives two well separated diffusion-controlled single waves ($E_{1/2} = -0.624$ V and -1.352 V vs S.C.E., respectively); both of which are irreversible and correspond to one-electron reduction processes, $Cu^{2+} \rightarrow Cu^+ \rightarrow Cu^0$.

Because of the irreversible but diffusion-controlled nature of these waves, it was possible to evaluate the kinetic parameters for these reduction processes in the usual manner^{9,4,7} and the results are given in Table 2.

Comparison with literature data shows that the copper(II) complex of this macrocyclic ligand is reduced at a more negative potential than in the case of $Cu(en)_2^{2+}$ and $Cu(gly)_2$ studied earlier⁹, which is expected for a complex of a strong field ligand. However, for the nickel(II) complex, the reduction is at a potential comparable to that for $Ni(en)_2^{2+}$ and only slightly more negative than that for $Ni(gly)_2$ ⁴. Also, unlike $Ni(\text{biguanide})_2^{2+}$ which is reduced reversibly⁴, the reduction of $[Ni(16)\text{-ane-N}_6]^{2+}$ is irreversible although both are low-spin square-planar complexes. But the rate of reduction of this nickel(II) complex is exceedingly much faster than that of $Ni(en)_2^{2+}$ under comparable conditions due to a much lower E_a value in agreement with the mechanism of electron transfer proposed earlier, according to which electron transfer to a nickel(II)

TABLE 2—ELECTROREDUCTION OF NICKEL(II) AND COPPER(II) COMPLEXES ML^{2+} ($L=[16]\text{-ane-N}_6$) AT DME ($h_{DE}=30$ cm; $m^{3/2}t^{1/2}=1.947$)

[Complex] = 0.001 M. Data at 25° in 0.1 M KOI + 0.002% Triton X-100

Complex	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs S.C.E.	$10^4 \cdot D^a$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	α	k_r $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	E_a kJ mol^{-1}
NiL ²⁺	1.350	0.85	0.404	1.65 ^b	74.4
CuL ²⁺					
1st wave	0.624	8.70	0.664	31.22 ^c	110.2
2nd wave	1.352	—	0.568	0.465 ^b	50.8

^a From measured conductance of 0.001 M aqueous solution of $ML(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ at 25°. ^b At potential of -1.6 V vs S.C.E.

^c At potential of -1.0 V vs S.C.E.

ion in a square-planar strong field ligand environment is expected to be very much faster⁴.

It is necessary to point out that the experimental value of the diffusion coefficient, D , of $[\text{Ni}(\text{16})\text{-ane-N}_6]^{2+}$ is ca. 1/10th of the value of $[\text{Cu}(\text{16})\text{-ane-N}_6]^{2+}$ (Table 2) which is rather intriguing since for the square-planar complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) formed by ethylenedibiguanide, $\text{M}(\text{endibigH}_2)^{2+}$, the D values are comparable (at 25° $10^6 \times D$, cm^2s^{-1} , values are 10.1 ($\text{M}=\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$) and 10.9 ($\text{M}=\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$)⁹.

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References

1. D. H. BUSCH, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 392.
2. D. K. CABBINESS and D. W. MARGERUM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 2151.
3. D. BANERJEA and P. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1321.
4. S. SENGUPTA, and D. BANERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 741.
5. K. B. NAIK and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 282.
6. D. BANERJEA and P. CHOWDHURY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 3259.
7. A. K. BANERJEE and D. BANERJEA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 937.
8. D. BANERJEA, "Fundamental Principles of Inorganic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Sultan Chand & Sons, New Delhi, 1984, p 357.
9. D Values at 25° calculated from ionic conductance (Λ) of $\text{M}(\text{endibigH}_2)^{2+}$ obtained from data quoted by P. RAY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 313 and using the equation for temperature correction, $\Lambda_t = \Lambda_{25} [1 + 0.02(t-25)]$.